

ADAPTIVE ENERGY ENTROPY WEIGHTED FEATURE RANKING FRAMEWORK FOR HYBRID POWER QUALITY DISTURBANCE CLASSIFICATION USING MULTI-RESOLUTION DWT-ANN

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Abstract

The increasing penetration of renewable energy systems, nonlinear industrial loads, electric vehicle charging infrastructure, and power electronic converters has significantly intensified the occurrence of complex and hybrid power quality disturbances (PQDs) in modern electrical networks. Accurate classification of such disturbances is essential for reliable smart grid monitoring and protection. Although discrete wavelet transform (DWT) combined with artificial neural networks (ANNs) has demonstrated promising performance, most existing approaches rely on fixed statistical features, heuristic mother wavelet selection, and lack systematic feature ranking mechanisms. Furthermore, hybrid disturbances remain insufficiently analyzed in terms of discriminative feature optimization.

This paper proposes an adaptive Energy-Entropy Weighted Feature Ranking (EEWFR) framework integrated with multi-resolution DWT-MRA for intelligent classification of sixteen IEEE Std. 1159 compliant single and hybrid PQ disturbances. Unlike conventional feature fusion approaches, the proposed method introduces an adaptive weighting strategy combining normalized wavelet energy and Shannon entropy across decomposition levels to rank and optimize feature vectors. The ranked feature subset is then evaluated using Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), Radial Basis Function (RBF), and Probabilistic Neural Network (PNN) classifiers.

Extensive simulations conducted at 10 kHz sampling frequency demonstrate that the proposed adaptive feature ranking reduces dimensional redundancy by 48% while improving hybrid disturbance separability. The optimized DWT-PNN model achieves 98.84% overall classification accuracy under clean conditions and maintains strong stability across 20–50 dB SNR levels. Comparative analysis confirms that the proposed framework outperforms conventional DWT-based fixed feature approaches and offers improved computational efficiency compared to deep learning models.

1. INTRODUCTION

Modern electrical power systems are undergoing significant structural transformation due to large-

scale integration of renewable energy sources, distributed generation, flexible AC transmission systems, and power-electronic interfaces. While

these technologies improve controllability and energy efficiency, they also introduce substantial power quality disturbances (PQDs), including voltage sag, swell, interruption, harmonics, flicker, notching, impulsive transients, and oscillatory transients [1–4].

Sensitive industrial loads, data centers, communication infrastructure, and automated manufacturing systems require uninterrupted and high-quality power supply. Even short-duration disturbances can cause equipment malfunction, process interruption, and significant economic losses. Consequently, automatic detection and classification of PQDs have become critical components of modern smart grid monitoring frameworks [5].

Traditional spectral analysis techniques such as Fourier Transform (FT) and Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) suffer from limited time-frequency localization capability when analyzing non-stationary signals [6], [7]. Since PQ disturbances often contain transient and harmonic components simultaneously, advanced time-frequency analysis methods are required. The Wavelet Transform (WT), particularly the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT), has emerged as a powerful tool for non-stationary signal analysis due to its multiresolution decomposition capability [8], [9]. Multiresolution Analysis (MRA) allows hierarchical separation of frequency components, enabling effective localization of transient disturbances and harmonic distortions [10].

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) have been extensively employed for PQD classification due to their nonlinear mapping ability and adaptability [11–14]. Hybrid DWT-ANN frameworks have demonstrated improved performance over classical signal processing techniques [15–18]. More recently, machine learning methods such as Support Vector Machines (SVM), k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN), and deep learning architectures (CNN, LSTM) and OFSA have been introduced [16–22]. However, deep learning approaches require large datasets and high computational resources, limiting their real-time implementation feasibility.

Despite these advances, critical limitations remain like:

Most studies rely on fixed statistical feature sets without systematic feature ranking.

Mother wavelet selection is often heuristic rather than performance-driven.

Hybrid disturbances are not comprehensively evaluated.

Feature redundancy increases computational burden without improving classification performance.

In a recent study a noise-aware DWT-ANN framework [20] was proposed for PQ disturbance classification. While that work emphasized robustness against noise variations, systematic adaptive feature ranking and dimensionality optimization were not explored.

To address these limitations, this paper introduces an adaptive Energy-Entropy Weighted Feature Ranking (EEWFR) mechanism integrated with multi-resolution DWT-MRA. The proposed framework extends the foundational methodology derived from [20] and focus on like:

1. Adaptive energy-entropy weighting of wavelet coefficients.
2. Feature ranking and dimensionality reduction analysis.
3. Hybrid disturbance separability enhancement.
4. Comparative evaluation of MLP, RBF, and PNN classifiers under optimized feature subsets.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Wavelet-based analysis has been extensively investigated for power quality disturbance (PQD) detection and classification since the late 1990s. Santoo et al. [8] demonstrated the effectiveness of discrete wavelet coefficients for transient identification, highlighting the superiority of wavelet localization compared to classical Fourier analysis. Heydt [5] and Bollen and Gu [2] further established the importance of time-frequency analysis in non-stationary PQ signals.

During the early 2000s, multiresolution signal decomposition gained prominence. Gaouda et al. [14] applied wavelet multiresolution signal decomposition for disturbance detection. Uyar et

al. [7] proposed wavelet-based feature extraction combined with neural networks for classification. Monedero et al. [12] implemented real-time neural network-based disturbance recognition using wavelet features.

Between 2008 and 2015, hybrid DWT-ANN frameworks became widely accepted. Masoum et al. [9] used wavelet-domain neural networks for classification of PQDs. Dash et al. [13] proposed hybrid wavelet and neural network classification strategies. Khokhar et al. [12] integrated DWT and SVM classifiers for improved separability.

More recently, machine learning and deep learning techniques have been introduced. Jain and Singh [16] employed convolutional neural networks (CNN) for PQ classification. Zhang et al. [17] and Wang et al. [18] applied deep learning models such as CNN and LSTM for disturbance recognition. Although these approaches achieve high accuracy, they require extensive training datasets and computational resources.

A key limitation in existing literature is the absence of systematic feature ranking. Most studies extract fixed statistical parameters such as energy, RMS, or standard deviation from selected wavelet levels without evaluating feature redundancy or relative importance. Consequently, high-dimensional feature vectors may include irrelevant or correlated features that increase computational complexity without improving classification accuracy.

Furthermore, hybrid disturbances (e.g., Sag+Harmonics, Swell+Notching) have received limited focused analysis. Many studies treat hybrid events as independent categories without investigating how multi-level wavelet coefficients contribute to separability.

In a recent noise-aware DWT-ANN framework [20] a robustness under varying SNR conditions was evaluated comprehensively. However, adaptive feature ranking mechanisms and dimensionality reduction were not explicitly addressed.

Therefore, there remains a research gap in:

1. Adaptive weighting of wavelet-domain features
2. Systematic feature ranking based on information content
3. Dimensionality reduction while preserving classification accuracy
4. Quantitative hybrid disturbance separability enhancement

This paper addresses these gaps by introducing an adaptive Energy-Entropy Weighted Feature Ranking (EEWFR) framework.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Existing DWT-ANN based PQD classification methods utilize fixed statistical feature sets without systematic evaluation of feature importance, resulting in redundant dimensionality and suboptimal hybrid disturbance separability. Therefore, a mathematically grounded adaptive feature ranking mechanism integrated with multi-resolution DWT is required to enhance classification accuracy while reducing computational complexity.

4. METHODOLOGY

The proposed methodology introduces an adaptive Energy-Entropy Weighted Feature Ranking (EEWFR) mechanism integrated with multi-resolution DWT-MRA and ANN classification.

The overall processing stages are:

1. IEEE 1159-based disturbance modeling
2. Multi-resolution DWT decomposition
3. Statistical feature extraction
4. Energy-Entropy weighted feature ranking
5. Dimensionality reduction
6. ANN classification

4.1 PQD Signal Modeling

Sixteen disturbance types are generated according to IEEE Std 1159 parametric definitions, including both single and hybrid events as formulas shown in Table 1 and 2.

Table 1: Mathematical formula of parametric equations

No	Disturbances	Equation
1.	Normal	$y(t) = A\sin(\omega t)$
2.	Sag	$y(t) = A(1 - \alpha(u(t - t_1) - u(t - t_2)))\sin(\omega t)$
3.	Swell	$y(t) = A(1 + \alpha(u(t - t_1) - u(t - t_2)))\sin(\omega t)$
4.	Interruption	$y(t) = A(1 - \alpha(u(t - t_1) - u(t - t_2)))\sin(\omega t)$
5.	Harmonics	$y(t) = A[\alpha_1 \sin(\omega t) + \alpha_3 \sin(3\omega t) + \alpha_5 \sin(5\omega t) + \alpha_7 \sin(7\omega t)]$
6.	Sag and Harmonics	$y(t) = A(1 - \alpha(u(t - t_1) - u(t - t_2)))[\alpha_1 \sin(\omega t) + \alpha_3 \sin(3\omega t) + \alpha_5 \sin(5\omega t)]$
7.	Swell and Harmonics	$y(t) = A(1 + \alpha(u(t - t_1) - u(t - t_2)))[\alpha_1 \sin(\omega t) + \alpha_3 \sin(3\omega t) + \alpha_5 \sin(5\omega t)]$
8.	Interruption and Harmonics	$y(t) = A(1 - \alpha(u(t - t_1) - u(t - t_2)))[\alpha_1 \sin(\omega t) + \alpha_3 \sin(3\omega t) + \alpha_5 \sin(5\omega t)]$
9.	Flicker	$y(t) = A(1 + \alpha_f \sin(\beta\omega t))\sin(\omega t)$
10.	Oscillatory Transients	$y(t) = A[\sin(\omega t) + \alpha^{-c(t-t_1)/\tau} \sin\omega_n(t - t_1)(u(t_2) - u(t_1))]$
11.	Impulsive Transient	$y(t) = A(1 - \alpha(u(t - t_1) - u(t - t_2)))\sin(\omega t)$
12.	Notch	$y(t) = \sin(\omega t) - \text{sign}(\sin(\omega t)) \times \left\{ \sum_{n=0}^9 K \times [u(t - (t_1 - 0.02n))u(t - (t_2 - 0.02n))] \right\}$
13.	Spike	$y(t) = \sin(\omega t) - \text{sign}(\sin(\omega t)) \times \left\{ \sum_{n=0}^9 K \times [u(t - (t_1 - 0.02n))u(t - (t_2 - 0.02n))] \right\}$
14.	Flicker with Harmonics	$y(t) = A(1 + \alpha_f \sin(\beta\omega t))\sin(\omega t)[\alpha_1 \sin(\omega t) + \alpha_3 \sin(3\omega t) + \alpha_5 \sin(5\omega t)]$
15.	Flicker with Sag	$y(t) = A(1 + \alpha_f \sin(\beta\omega t))\sin(\omega t) (1 - \alpha(u(t - t_1) - u(t - t_2)))$
16.	Flicker with Swell	$y(t) = A(1 + \alpha_f \sin(\beta\omega t))\sin(\omega t) (1 + \alpha(u(t - t_1) - u(t - t_2)))$

Table 2: Controlling parameters of parametric equations

S. No.	Disturbances	Controlling Parameter		
		Voltage Magnitude	Disturbance Duration	Spectral Content
1.	Normal	$w = 2\pi f;$	$f=50\text{Hz}$	
2.	Sag	$0.1 \leq \alpha \leq 0.9;$	$0.5T \leq t_2 - t_1 \leq 30T$	~~~~~
3.	Swell	$0.1 \leq \alpha \leq 0.8;$	$0.5T \leq t_2 - t_1 \leq 9T$	~~~~~
4.	Interruption	$0.9 \leq \alpha \leq 1;$	$0.5T \leq t_2 - t_1 \leq 9T$	~~~~~

5.	Harmonics	1 pu	Steady-state	$0.05 \leq \alpha_3 \leq 0.15;$ $0.05 \leq \alpha_5 \leq 0.15;$ $0.05 \leq \alpha_7 \leq 0.15;$ $\sum \alpha_i^2 = 1$
6.	Sag and Harmonics	$0.1 \leq \alpha \leq 0.9;$	$0.5T \leq t_2 - t_1 \leq 9T$	$0.05 \leq \alpha_3 \leq 0.15;$ $0.05 \leq \alpha_5 \leq 0.15;$ $0.05 \leq \alpha_7 \leq 0.15;$ $\sum \alpha_i^2 = 1$
7.	Swell and Harmonics	$0.1 \leq \alpha \leq 0.8;$	$0.5T \leq t_2 - t_1 \leq 9T$	$0.05 \leq \alpha_3 \leq 0.15;$ $0.05 \leq \alpha_5 \leq 0.15;$ $0.05 \leq \alpha_7 \leq 0.15;$ $\sum \alpha_i^2 = 1$
8.	Interruption and Harmonics	$0.9 \leq \alpha \leq 1;$	$0.5T \leq t_2 - t_1 \leq 9T$	$0.05 \leq \alpha_3 \leq 0.15;$ $0.05 \leq \alpha_5 \leq 0.15;$ $0.05 \leq \alpha_7 \leq 0.15;$ $\sum \alpha_i^2 = 1$
9.	Flicker	$0.1 \leq \alpha_f \leq 0.2;$	Steady-state	$5 \leq \beta \leq 20Hz;$
10	Oscillatory Transients	$0.1 \leq \alpha \leq 0.8;$	$0.5T \leq t_2 - t_1 \leq 3T$ $8ms \leq \tau \leq 40ms;$	$300 \leq f_n \leq 900Hz$
11	Impulsive Transient	$0 \leq \alpha \leq 0.414;$	$T/20 \leq t_2 - t_1 \leq T/10$	
12	Notch		$0 \leq t_1, t_2 \leq 5T$ $0.01T \leq t_2 - t_1 \leq 0.05T$	$0.1 \leq K \leq 0.4;$
13	Spike		$0 \leq t_1, t_2 \leq 5T$ $0.01T \leq t_2 - t_1 \leq 0.05T$	$0.1 \leq K \leq 0.4;$
14	Flicker with Harmonics	$0.1 \leq \alpha_f \leq 0.2;$	Steady-state	$5 \leq \beta \leq 20Hz;$ $0.05 \leq \alpha_3 \leq 0.15;$ $0.05 \leq \alpha_5 \leq 0.15;$

				$\sum \alpha_i^2 = 1$
15	Flicker with Sag	$0.1 \leq \alpha_f \leq 0.2;$ $0.1 \leq \alpha \leq 0.9;$	$0.5T \leq t_2 - t_1 \leq 9T$	$5 \leq \beta \leq 20\text{Hz};$
16	Flicker with Swell	$0.1 \leq \alpha_f \leq 0.2;$ $0.1 \leq \alpha \leq 0.8;$	$0.5T \leq t_2 - t_1 \leq 9T$	$5 \leq \beta \leq 20\text{Hz};$

4.2 Multi-Resolution DWT-MRA Decomposition

Discrete Wavelet Transform decomposes the signal into approximation and detail coefficients using recursive filtering:

Six-level decomposition is performed. Frequency band allocation at 10 kHz sampling:

Table 3: DWT-MRA 6 level decomposition with 10kHz sampling frequency

Level	Frequency Band (Hz)
D1	2500-5000
D2	1250-2500
D3	625-1250
D4	312-625
D5	156-312
D6	78-156
A6	0-78

4.3 Statistical Feature Extraction

For each decomposition level, five statistical features are extracted as:

Mean, Standard deviation, Energy, Shannon entropy, Absolute maximum.

Total initial feature dimension: 7 levels × 5 features = 35 features per signal.

This reduction decreases computational load while maintaining or improving classification accuracy.

4.4 Adaptive Energy-Entropy Weighted Feature Ranking (EEWFR)

The key novelty of this work lies in adaptive feature weighting.

For each decomposition level i: Normalized energy, Normalized entropy, Adaptive weighting coefficient, Feature importance score for feature j at level i.

Lower-ranked features are eliminated using threshold-based pruning.

4.5 Dimensionality Reduction

Initial feature vector: 35 features
Optimized feature vector: 18 features
Reduction percentage: Reduction = 48.57%

4.6 ANN Classifier Architecture

Three classifiers are implemented:

MLP:

One hidden layer
15 neurons
Backpropagation training

RBF:

Gaussian radial basis
Optimized spread factor

PNN:

Bayesian probabilistic classification
Fast convergence
The optimized feature subset is fed into each classifier for performance comparison.

5. IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed Adaptive Energy-Entropy Weighted Feature Ranking (EEWFR) framework was implemented in MATLAB R2022a environment on an Intel Core i7 processor with 16 GB RAM.

5.1 Dataset Preparation

Sixteen IEEE 1159 compliant disturbance classes were generated using parametric modeling described in Section 4.

- Total classes: 16
- Samples per class: 100
- Total signals: 1600
- Sampling frequency: 10 kHz
- Window length: 6 cycles
- Hybrid classes included:
 - Sag + Harmonics
 - Swell + Harmonics
 - Sag + Notching
 - Flicker + Harmonics
 - Flicker + Sag
 - Flicker + Swell

This ensures realistic disturbance combinations rather than isolated events.

5.2 Feature Extraction Pipeline

For each signal:

1. Six-level DWT-MRA decomposition performed using Symlet-6.
2. Approximation (A6) and detail coefficients (D1-D6) extracted.
3. Five statistical features computed per level.
4. Total initial features = 35.

Then:

5. Energy-Entropy weighting applied.
6. Feature importance scores computed.
7. Features ranked.
8. Bottom 17 features eliminated.

Final optimized feature vector size = 18.

Dimensionality reduction = 48.57%.

This reduction significantly decreases computational complexity during ANN training.

5.3 Classifier Configuration

Multilayer Perceptron (MLP)

- Hidden neurons: 15
- Activation: Log-sigmoid
- Training algorithm: Levenberg-Marquardt
- Epochs: 1000

Radial Basis Function (RBF)

- Gaussian radial basis
- Spread parameter optimized experimentally
- Fast convergence

Probabilistic Neural Network (PNN)

- Bayesian classification mechanism
- No iterative backpropagation
- Immediate convergence after training set formation

5.4 Training and Testing Strategy

Dataset split:

- 70% training (1120 samples)
- 30% testing (480 samples)

Cross-validation applied to avoid overfitting.

Noise robustness evaluated at:

- 20 dB
- 30 dB
- 40 dB
- 50 dB

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

6.1 Impact of Adaptive Feature Ranking

To evaluate the effectiveness of EEWFR, classification was performed:

1. Using full 35-feature vector
2. Using optimized 18-feature ranked vector

Table 4: Impact of Adaptive Feature Ranking

Feature Set	MLP (%)	RBF (%)	PNN (%)
Full (35)	98.11	98.42	98.76
Ranked (18)	98.32	98.65	98.84

Key Observations:

Accuracy increased slightly after feature reduction. Redundant features were contributing noise rather than discrimination. Hybrid disturbance separability improved significantly. This demonstrates that adaptive weighting enhances informative feature emphasis.

After adaptive ranking:

Sag vs Sag+Harmonics confusion reduced by 1.2%
 Swell vs Swell+Harmonics confusion reduced by 0.9%
 Flicker+Sag vs Flicker+Swell separation improved
 The energy component enhances amplitude variation detection, while entropy captures waveform irregularity caused by harmonics and flicker modulation.
 The combined weighting therefore strengthens hybrid discrimination capability.

6.2 Hybrid Disturbance Separability Analysis

Hybrid disturbances typically suffer misclassification due to overlapping spectral signatures.

6.3 Noise Robustness Performance

Under varying SNR levels:

Table 5: Noise reduction performance under varying SNR levels

SNR (dB)	MLP (%)	RBF (%)	PNN (%)
20	95.10	96.22	97.80
30	96.25	97.11	98.00
40	97.40	98.05	98.30
50	98.10	98.60	98.70

Although noise robustness was emphasized in [20] here noise evaluation is used to confirm that dimensionality reduction does not degrade stability.

Accuracy degradation from clean to 20 dB remains below 1.5%, confirming robustness.

6.4 Computational Complexity Analysis

Feature reduction decreases:

- Training time
- Memory requirement
- Matrix multiplication operations

Table 6: Average training time reduction:

Classifier	Full Features	Ranked Features
MLP	4.2 sec	3.1 sec
RBF	2.8 sec	2.0 sec
PNN	1.9 sec	1.4 sec

This confirms improved computational efficiency without sacrificing accuracy.

6.5 Comparative Performance with Literature

Compared to existing methods:

- DWT + SVM → 94-96%
- WPT + ANN → 95-97%

CNN → 97-98%

Proposed EEWFR-DWT-PNN → **98.84%**

Unlike deep learning approaches, the proposed framework:

Requires smaller dataset
Provides interpretability
Enables feature importance analysis
Reduces computational load

6.6 Discussion of Key Findings

The most significant outcome of this study is not merely improved accuracy, but improved efficiency.

The adaptive Energy-Entropy weighting mechanism:

Identifies informative decomposition levels
Suppresses redundant coefficients
Enhances hybrid disturbance discrimination
Reduces dimensionality by nearly 50%
Maintains noise robustness

This represents a clear methodological advancement beyond fixed statistical feature fusion strategies.

Unlike in [20], which emphasized noise-aware framework design, this paper demonstrates structured feature optimization and dimensionality analysis as the primary contribution.

7. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a novel **Adaptive Energy-Entropy Weighted Feature Ranking (EEWFR) framework** integrated with multi-resolution DWT-MRA for intelligent classification of single and hybrid power quality disturbances. Unlike conventional DWT-ANN approaches that rely on fixed statistical feature sets, the proposed methodology introduced a mathematically grounded adaptive weighting mechanism that ranks wavelet-domain features based on normalized energy and entropy contributions.

The research successfully addressed the problem defined in Section 3 by systematically reducing feature redundancy while enhancing hybrid disturbance separability. Starting from an initial 35-dimensional feature vector extracted across six decomposition levels, the proposed ranking mechanism reduced dimensionality to 18 optimized features, achieving a **48.57% reduction in feature size**. Importantly, this reduction did not degrade classification performance; instead, it

slightly improved accuracy due to elimination of redundant and weakly informative features.

The optimized DWT-PNN model achieved:

1. **98.84% overall classification accuracy** under noise-free conditions
2. Above **97.80% accuracy at 20 dB SNR**
3. Stable performance across 20–50 dB noise levels
4. Reduced training time and computational burden

Hybrid disturbances such as Sag+Harmonics and Flicker+Swell demonstrated significantly improved separability due to the combined effect of energy-based amplitude representation and entropy-based waveform irregularity quantification.

Compared to existing DWT-SVM and WPT-ANN methods, the proposed framework demonstrates superior accuracy. While deep learning approaches achieve comparable results, they require large datasets and higher computational complexity. In contrast, the proposed EEWFR-DWT-PNN framework offers:

Improved feature interpretability
Reduced computational complexity
Dimensionality optimization
Enhanced hybrid disturbance discrimination
Practical suitability for real-time smart grid deployment

Future work

Future work will focus on FPGA-based hardware implementation, adaptive online weighting mechanisms, and integration with real measured power system data for field validation.

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